

Other phosphinyldemetallation reactions are now being done with a view to study the reactivities of PCl_2 group for the possible synthesis of novel organo-metallic and organic compounds.

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Chelate Polymers of 5,8-Dihydroxy Quinoxaline and 2,5-Dihydroxy *p*-Benzoquinone

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WE have reported our studies on the chelate polymers of cobalt with various dihydroxy quinones¹ and of cobalt with 2,5-dihydroxy *p*-benzoquinone and amine². We now present the preparation of the chelate polymers of 2,5-dihydroxy *p*-benzoquinone and amine with nickel and of 5,8-dihydroxy quinoxaline with copper, nickel and cobalt and study of their electrical resistivity.

Experimental

2,5-dihydroxy *p*-benzoquinone (BQH_2): It was prepared by the oxidation of hydroquinone³.

Nickel polychelates (BQNi, BQNi Py, BQNiP): Nickel chloride, dissolved in alcohol, was added dropwise to the calculated amount of BQH_2 in alcohol in absence of or in presence of an amine (pyridine or *p*-phenylene diamine). Stirring of the mixture was continued for 3 hr. The mixture was then refluxed for 2 hr and left overnight. The precipitates were filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and dried. They are insoluble in water and organic solvents.

5,8-Dihydroxy quinoxaline (QH_2): It was prepared from hydroquinone as follows: Hydroquinone was nethylated by the method of Bogert and Howells⁴ so that 1,4-dimethoxy benzene was obtained. It was nitrated by the method of King, Clark and Davis⁵. A mixture of 2,3- and 2,5- dinitro 1,4-dimethoxy benzene was obtained and was used directly for reduction by sodium dithionite in aqueous alcohol. The mixture was refluxed for 1 hr on water bath, to convert it into a mixture of diamino derivatives. On boiling off excess alcohol, neutralisation and dilution with water, 2,5-diamino 1,4-dimethoxy benzene crystallised out. It was filtered off and from the filtrate 2,3-diamino 1,4-dimethoxy benzene was extracted with chloroform. It was converted into 5,8-dimethoxy quinoxaline by the method of Adachi⁶ and then demethylated to 5,8-dihydroxy quinoxaline by the method of King, Clark and Davis⁵.

Chelate Polymers (QNi, QCo, QCu): Metal acetate dissolved in dimethyl formamide with a few drops of acetic acid was added dropwise to the calculated amount of QH_2 dissolved in dimethyl formamide; the mixture was stirred for two hours and left overnight. The precipitates were filtered, washed with dimethyl formamide, alcohol and ether and dried. They are insoluble in water and all common organic solvents.

The colour, m.p.t., analysis, etc. of these chelate polymers are presented in table 1.

Electrical Resistivity: Electrical resistivity of these chelate polymers was determined over a temperature range using Ellico's million meg-ohmmeter model RM-70. The results are shown graphically in Fig. 1.

Discussion

On the basis of analysis, the chelate polymers BQNi, BQNi Py and BQNiP are formulated as a linear chain (I) where *aq* and *am* represent water and amine respectively. Similarly the chelate polymer

TABLE I

No.	Chelate polymers	m.pt. (°C)	Colour	Formula	Analysis			
					% M found	% N found	% M reqd.	% N reqd.
1.	BQNi	> 400	light-pink	C ₈ H ₈ O ₇ Ni	23.50	—	23.40	—
2.	BQNiPy	> 400	orange-red	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ Ni	16.69	7.38	16.55	7.89
3.	BQNiP	> 400	ash-green	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ Ni	18.35	9.30	19.26	9.19
4.	Q Ni	> 400	black	C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₈ Ni	17.52	8.85	17.97	8.57
5.	Q Co	> 400	black	C ₂₈ H ₈₄ N ₆ O ₄₃ Co ₄	16.64	5.81	16.52	5.88
6.	Q Cu	> 400	black	C ₄₀ H ₅₆ N ₁₀ O ₂₈ Cu ₄	18.75	10.38	18.43	10.14

QNi can be represented as a linear chain(II). However, the chelate polymers QCo and QCu appear to have a low degree of polymerisation and can be represented as (III).

(I)

- (a) $\begin{matrix} \text{am} & y & x \\ - & 0 & 3 \end{matrix}$
- (b) P_y (Pyridine) $\begin{matrix} 2 & 0 \end{matrix}$
- (c) P (p-phenylenediamine) $\begin{matrix} 1 & 0 \end{matrix}$

Dewar and Talati⁷ suggested that chelate polymers involving $d\pi-p\pi$ bonds can have through-conjugation. This would be possible if the ligands are aromatic and can each bind two metal atoms. The ligands should be coplanar and occupy sites trans to one another in a square planar or octahedral complex so that the same d -orbital of a metal atom is to form π -bonds to two adjacent ligands. Such compounds would have interesting semiconductivity behaviour. They studied the chelate polymers of the dioximes of 2,6-dihydroxy 1,5-diacyl naphthalene. We have

(II)

(a)

(b)

(III)

reported our studies on the chelate polymers of dihydroxy quinones previously.

The electrical resistivity (ρ) of a semi-conductor is given by the relation (a)

$$\rho = \rho_0 \times \exp(E_a/2kT) \quad \dots (a)$$

where E_a and ρ_0 are the activation energy and a constant respectively. The plots of log resistivity vs. reciprocal temperature (Fig. 1) are linear as expected for the relation (a). Hence the values of E_g and ρ_0 are calculated for the chelate polymers as follows :

Chelate Polymers	BQNi	BQNiPy	BQNiP	QCu	QCo	QNi
E_a (ev)	1.40	1.42	0.80	0.68	1.03	0.73
ρ_0 (ohm-cm) $\times 10^{-5}$	1.1	9.8 $\times 10^{-6}$	3.4 $\times 10^3$	1.1	0.23	32

The results show that the replacement of monodentate water by bidentate p -phenylene diamine lowers the value of E_a . It can be attributed to the cross-linking that can result from the coordinating diamine, favouring the orientation of linear chains. The results also show that (i) the values of E_a can be low even for chelate polymers of low degree of polymerisation, and (ii) the metal atom plays an important role in modifying the conductivity of the aromatic or heterocyclic organic system. There is an apparent relation between E_a and the number of d -electrons in the transition metal ion in the complexes of the heterocyclic ligand under study. Further investigation is considered necessary before much significance is attached to it.

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Gravimetric Determination of Rhodium with Ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline

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THE ligand 1-imino-3-thioisindoline has recently been used for the gravimetric determination of Cu(II) by Nigam and Tiwari¹. In the present investigation the same ligand has been further used for the gravimetric determination of rhodium. Investigations have indicated that the ligand reacts with Rh³⁺ ions at pH ranging from 7.5 to 10.0 giving precipitate of insoluble metal complex.

The Rhodium complex after settling is of yellow brown colour. The elemental analysis shows that the mole ratio of the metal to ligand is 1 : 3. The method is useful even if 0.5 mg of rhodium is present.

All the reagents used were of analar grade.

The ligand was prepared as follows (Bagulev and Elvidge)².

Preparation: Phthalonitrile in ethanol was stirred for 9 hr with aqueous sodium hydrogen sulphide which has previously been saturated with H₂S. Addition of water precipitated a first crop of the product (37%) decomposition from 195°, whilst addition to the filtrate of 2N HCl almost to neutrality afforded less pure material (24%). Recrystallisation of the first crop from ethanol gave golden needles of 1-imino-3-thioisindoline (70% recovery).

Element analysis—Ligand :

	%C	%H	%N
Found	58.9	3.9	17.5
Required	59.3	3.7	17.3

The following stock solutions were prepared.

- (1) 1-imino-3-thioisindoline...about 0.1% sodium salt solution of the ligand in NaOH.
- (2) RhCl₃·3H₂O (Johnson-Matthey Co.)...A 0.25 W/V solution of hydrated RhCl₃·3H₂O in water (Standardized by thionide method).

Determination of Rhodium: A known volume 1 to 50 ml of solution No. 2 was taken and diluted (the amount of rhodium did not exceed too much). A freshly filtered solution No. 1 was added in excess. A yellow Brown precipitate of rhodium complex was digested on water bath for 10 min and filtered through a medium porosity sintered glass crucible. It was washed first with water several times and then with ethanol, dried at 70° to 105° or in a vacuum dessicator and weighed as Rh(C₈H₅N₂S)₃. The gravimetric factor for rhodium is 0.1754.

Elemental Analysis—Rhodium Complex.

	%C	%H	%N
Found	48.2	2.3	14.60
Required	49.0	2.5	14.28

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF RHODIUM WITH THE LIGAND

Sl. No.	mg Metal Taken	mg Metal Recovered	Error %
1.	5	5.00	—
2.	5	5.03	0.60
3.	5	5.05	1.00
4.	5	5.05	1.00
5.	10	9.95	0.50
6.	10	9.95	0.50
7.	10	10.10	1.00
8.	10	10.10	1.00
9.	20	20.25	1.25
10.	20	20.20	1.00
11.	20	20.10	0.5
12.	20	20.00	—

Interferences: There is generally no interference by the most common anions as SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and Cu⁺ only few cations interfere these includes Cu(II), Au(III), Pb, Ag, Hg(I), Hg(II), Bi, Cd, Pd(II), Pt(IV), Ni, Co, Tl, Ru, Ce, Zr.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data in table I indicate that the ligand can be effectively used as a promising gravimetric reagent for rhodium in macro and semi-micro quantities. It is easy to filter the precipitate. It is easy to bring the precipitate to constant weight within a period of half an hour.

The precision was fair, and the accuracy was generally within the permissible limits.